
Government initiatives and their implications on the Tiwa tribe of Assam: A Sociological Study

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ABSTRACT

Northeast India is renowned for its beauty. Ethnic diversity, different attributes of racial and linguistic groups, natural resources, geophysical characteristics, and other attributes determine and enhance its beauty. The relationship among all the groups is unique and peaceful. Assam is geographically located in the middle of all northeastern states, and many ethnic groups have stayed here since time immemorial. The Tiwa is one of the significant tribal groups of Assam. Despite having a very rich and dynamic culture, they do not have adequate chances and exposure to improve their socioeconomic condition. The government has implemented several programs and initiatives to improve their economic condition, education facilities, health, sanitation, etc. They also try to maintain and promote their ethnic identity by establishing tribal museums and research centers for future generations. This research aims to analyze the government's policies and their implications for the Tiwas of Assam.

Introduction

The Tiwas, are a major ethnic group of Assam. They live in both the hills and plains of Assam. Racially they are belonging to the Mongoloid stock. Most of the tribal population of Assam are Indo-Mongoloids. Indo- Mongoloids came to Assam in different ways in different periods. The Tiwas

linguistically come under the Tibeto-Burman speech family like many other tribes of Assam belonging to the larger Bodo group of tribes (Borah, 2009).

Earlier they were known as *Lalung* by the Karbis and other neighboring groups. The word *La* means water and *Lung* means rescued. As a people of margins, they were referred to as a *Datialiya* in Ahom Buranjis. After independence, as in the case of many other tribes like the Abors, Mikirs, etc, they too developed a tendency to change their tribal name as they felt that the term Lalung was given and used in a derogatory sense by the non-Lalung population and finally, they emerged the term Lalung and replacing it with the term Tiwa. There emerged a feeling among the Lalungs that this name to their group was given by others and they started preferring the name Tiwas for themselves. They feel very insulted or derogated by the word Lalung.

About the origin of the *Tiwa* tribe, are some mythological stories. They believed that once lord Shiva was heavily intoxicated with rice beer. While he was sleeping some drops of his saliva oozed out from his mouth. And from those divine liquids, the lord created two human beings- male and female and out of this couple the *Tiwa* originated. (Thakur,1972)

Another story is that the *Tiwas* were the subjects of King Bali. He was the worshiper of lord Vishnu. And he desired that all his subjects should follow the royal religion. Those who do not follow that imprint a red mark on their forehead and turn out from the country. From that red(*lal*) mark they were known as *Lalung* (Thakur,1972).

The word *Lalung* is derived from the word *lang- lu* in Karbi which means light blue water. The hill *Lalungs* hold that the *lalung* word came from the word *libung* which means man to denote the entire tribe. According to them, *TI* means water and *WA* means superior. Also, the word *Tiwa* is derived from *ti- phar- wali* means a clan living near water. They believe that their first king *Sotonga Raja* was born out of water in Jayantia Hills (Gohain,1993).

Population and distribution of the Tiwa tribe of Assam – According to the 2011 Census report, the total *Tiwa* population is 200915. In 1872 the total *Tiwa* population was 34,859. In 1881 it was 47,650, in 1891 it was 52423. But suddenly for the Kalasar epidemic population decreased to 35513 in 1901. In Morigaon district 84.54% and in Nagaon district 62.92% of *Tiwa* population are concentrated. The plain *Tiwa* are mostly found in Nagaon, Morigaon, Kamrup, Kaliabor, Lanka, Sadiya, Dhemaji, and

Lakhimpur. The hill *Tiwa* lives in Karbi Anglong and some parts of the North Cachar and Jayantiya hills.¹ The hill Tiwa is found in the Amri, Chinthong, Rongkjang, Howraghat, etc (Patar,2021).

The hill Tiwas of Karbi Anglong district are not recognized as a scheduled tribe; recently only for academic and other purposes, they were certified as scheduled tribes. Also, they have not yet gotten the full status as a scheduled tribe in the Karbi Anglong district (Gohain,1993).

Relationship between Hill and Plain Tiwa tribe of Assam

Most of the tribal groups are mongoloid origin and they came to Assam and northeast India from China. During the different time phases, they were migrated for many reasons. After the migration from Tibet, they settled down in the hills and foothills areas of the Northeast. Earlier they were engaged in collecting food from the forest and meat for survival and engaged in horticulture and beekeeping. They were also involved in the community hunting process, where they used bow, arrow, and fire for hunting. In the hill area when the tribal people learned to live in a settled manner, they engaged in Jhum cultivation or shifting cultivation. Rice is the staple food for the hill and the plain Tiwas. Along with the rice they also produced cotton, long pepper, vegetables, and oranges. Jhum is a dominant form of cultivation of the hill economy (Guha, 1991). The economy of hills and plains was closely attached and interdependent. From the ancient period, they exchanged their product according to their needs. To fulfill their needs they are also engaged in barter systems for the surplus rice, dried fish, silk, and other goods of the plains. The main object of the barter system was to distribute the surplus produce (Chowdhury, 2015). In the Brahmaputra valley, several narrow routes across the hills have facilitated trade and migration from immemorial times. The people of the hill area used to come down to the plains for barter in winter. Some of them settled on the banks of streams in the foothills areas to make life easier and to serve as a bridge between the hills and the plains. The barter exchange system was the backbone of their lives. The Tiwa tribe is still very famous for continuing its traditional barter system. They celebrate this exchange system as a symbolic representation of their traditional practice. Apart from this, they are continuing the practice of community fishing. The Tiwa tribe is a unique tribe, that has two subgroups- hill and plain Tiwas. Though both groups have originated and migrated from the same place and practice the same

¹. (Census Report, 2011), Office of the Director of Census Operations, Assam, Bhangagarh, Guwahati-781005.

ritualistic beliefs, due to the continuous process of interaction or assimilation the plain Tiwas have faced challenges in maintaining their age-old practices. They have started to adopt the culture of the dominant Assamese group. Significantly, the hill Tiwas are still following the matrilineal descent system and plain Tiwas are following the patrilineal descent system. The system of ‘Shamadi’ (youth dormitory) is also not found among the plain Tiwas. However, the hill Tiwas spend their time in Traditional ‘Shamadi’. Many religious practices and festivals are also changing.

The Tiwa tribe and government initiatives

The relationship between the tribal communities and the government of India is remarkable from various points of view. The Indian Constitution of 1950 recognized them as ‘Scheduled tribes’ and protected them by special legislation. Regarding the administration of the scheduled areas, the governor of each state which includes a scheduled area is bound to submit a report to the president annually or whenever required. The states periodically prepare lists of scheduled tribes, and these have to be confirmed by parliament (Von and Haimendorf, 1982).

In 1886 during the colonial period, the British government implemented many policies related to the forest, land, and the tribal communities of Assam. Under the Assam Land and Revenue Regulation Law, 1886 by the British, certain regions were recognized as a tribal belt or tribal block in Assam, which was enacted by the Assam Government in 1947 by the first Chief Minister of Assam (Gopinath Bordoloi) and later governments also focused to preserve the land rights of the aboriginal backward. Their main motive was to protect the tribal classes from immigrants in regions where they were prominent because they were primitive and mainly backward.²

The Constitution of India has many safeguards for the Scheduled Tribes under Articles 15(4), 16(4), 16(4A), 16(4B), 19(5), 23, 24, 46, 164(1), 244, 244A, 320(4), 243D, 243T, 275(1), 330, 332, 334, 335, 338A, 339, 350A, 371A, 371B, 371C, and the Fifth and Sixth Schedules. Besides these constitutional provisions, both state and central governments initiated some major programs to ensure their socio-economic development. Under the sixth schedule of the Indian Constitution, there are three Autonomous Councils formed by the Government of Assam under different legislations for the overall development of six plain tribes, which are Mising, Rabha, Tiwa, Deori, Thengal Kachari, and Sonowal Kachari. Three

². Protected tribal belts and blocks in Assam - Wikipedia

Autonomous Councils are established under the constitutional provisions Bodoland Territorial Council, Karbi Anglong

Autonomous Council, and Dima Hasao Autonomous Council also six Autonomous Councils constituted under the legislations of the State of Assam for the socio-economic and cultural development of six plain tribes, the Tiwa Autonomous Council was established under the Tiwa Autonomous Council Act, 1995 (Saloi, 2015). Despite several measures adopted in the successive five-year plan, the activities have not been able to satisfy the aspirations of the tribal people.

The Constitution of India ensures the political representation of Scheduled Tribes in the Lower House of the Parliament and the State Legislative Assemblies through reserved seats. Article 15(4) of the Indian Constitution provides a seat reservation system in educational institutions for the scheduled tribes. Furthermore, the system of reservation based on the different categories or the system of quotas for educational purposes and in the government employment system also enables the scheduled tribe people to better their academic status. To give them full democratic freedom the Panchayat Raj system focused on promoting the political consciousness among the villagers. They also give importance to protecting the rights of the scheduled tribes, empowering the Gram Sabha, conserving natural resources, etc. They are also responsible for collecting fees from markets and fairs etc.

Another crucial scheme is the Assam Tribal Development Authority enacting the 'Family Oriented Income Generating Scheme' (FOIGS) as an anti-poverty measure for the upliftment of the Socio-Economic condition of tribal people as well as to generate self-employment opportunities for tribal families, living below the poverty line. It provides them with a sustainable way of livelihood.

The communication system in the rural tribal areas is still not very satisfactory. Therefore, to improve the communication system, the Assam Tribal Development Authority has taken up construction works of link roads, link bridges, culverts, etc. under the scheme. However, the road of West Karbi Anglong District, which is the homeland of the Hill Tiwa people is not in very good condition. In most of the rural areas drinking water facilities are not sufficient. As a consequence, the Assam Tribal Development Authority (ATDA) has provided financial help for the installation of ring wells, tube wells, and other infrastructure.

The youth dormitory is one of the major institutions in the Tiwa society. Earlier, they spend their time and learn vocational education in those dormitories. However, with the help of the central government, ATDA launched another scheme for the scheduled tribes. One hundred percent of central assistance is

given to those newly established vocational institutions for the smooth running of vocational training within the tribal areas. Besides vocational training, the government implemented schemes to provide economic assistance such as textbooks, school uniforms, and bicycles to the poor tribal students pursuing the pre-matric course and to encourage them to continue their education (Purkayastha, 2015).

The role of The Tiwa Autonomous Council is also significant, which was constituted for the upliftment of the Tiwa people. To preserve their ethnic identity and the overall development the Tiwa Autonomous Council was formed in April 1995. They selected their representative as the members of Council to improve their lives. There are certain village councils under the autonomous council. The central government also provides various funds to fulfill their needs. Due to the reason that the Tiwa, Rabha, and Mising tribes have no constitutional legality, funds are not directly provided to them. The funds are provided by the state government, and the central government has no responsibility for these autonomous councils. Land revenue power which was an objective to protect the Tiwas from illegal transfer of land to non-tribals is still not handed over to the council. So, it cannot collect revenue from the land for its own fund. The developmental works of the Tiwa Autonomous Council area are- the establishment of Tiwa Krishti Bhawan, the construction of the *Borghar* (Religious place) in some villages, the Construction of the boundary wall of a *Namghar* in Damal village, Two village roads were constructed, the distribution of small pump sets amongst the few cultivators, distribution of yarn for weaving among the weavers, distribution of *Teen Paats* (aluminum sheets used in roofing the House) for roofing houses among a few poor families, provided Desk and Benches in some schools basically in the primary schools, one ambulance provided in the Damal area by Tiwa Autonomous council.

The council also aimed to provide educational advantages to the Tiwa people from the primary to higher education level, but still, they are not able to establish a single Tiwa language school. The process of teacher requirement is also in the hands of the State government. Markets and fairs, ghats, and ferries may be a source of revenue for the council however, it may create conflict between the council and the Gaon Panchayat as the Panchayat system exists in the council area. After all, the Tiwa Autonomous Council is dependent on the state government. The general council shall have the executive powers over the council area. The Demand for political autonomy by the Tiwas in Assam is not only a political issue, but it has its roots in the overall socio-economic conditions of the Tiwas.

Presently, the state government is concentrating on preserving and promoting their ethnic identity by constructing tribal research institutes and museums for future generations. The material culture of the

tribes of Assam such as Tiwas, Karbis, Rengmas, Hmars, Dimasa Kacharis, Rabhas, Bodos, Misings, Sonowal Kacharis, Tamangs, and others are showcased in the display board of the galley in a tribe-specific fashion. In a section, they showcase the rare and exquisite ethnic jewellery of the tribes and are maintained in a separate room for exhibiting the same. Besides this Assam government also trained officials of development departments posted in Tribal areas and organized the program for skill development of unemployed ST/SC youth. Through the concept of model villages government tries to prevent distress migration from rural to urban areas, which is a common phenomenon in India's villages due to a lack of opportunities and facilities that guarantee a decent standard of living.³.

Conclusion

Though there are lots of initiatives and major policies implemented by the government and the Autonomous Council, there are some major factors, which make a hindrance to the overall development of the tribe. Most of the people of Assam are agriculturists and the Tiwas are no exception to this. Though the Tiwas are dependent on agricultural activities, the hill Tiwas are far away from the use of modern technology in the field of agriculture. Due to the lack of sufficient cultivable land for which hill Tiwa people are forced to use the highlands on hillocks for their agricultural purposes. They are mostly engaged in *Jhum* (shifting) cultivation. Due to a shortage of cultivable lands as well as a lack of modern technological use in the agricultural field, the production is not sufficient for their maintenance. Permanent land settlement for the Tiwas in the hilly regions has not been done. As a result, most of the Tiwa people in the hills don't have their 'Patta' though they have been possessing a particular plot of land since immemorial. Assam Land and Revenue Regulation Act has not been implemented sincerely.

On the other hand, it appears to the Committee that the officials in charge of enforcing the provisions, rather than protecting the interests of the tribal people of the region in such Belts and Blocks, have frequently violated the provisions, allowing illegal people and the transfer of lands to non-tribals through corrupt means. Many of these infiltrators have been able to get land settlement or mutation, as well as registration of sale deeds, through the help of these corrupt officials. Because of the negligence of the government officials to evict the encroachers, their number is increasing day by day and brings a serious

³ . Ethnographic Museum, Directorate of Assam Institute of Research for Tribals & Scheduled Castes, Government of Assam, India.

threat to the existence of the tribal people. The Tiwa people living in various tribal Belts and areas have been facing the same issue and they are losing their lands (Kachari, 2015).

Another important factor is the construction of the Nagaon Paper Mill, a unit of Hindustan Paper Corporation Ltd., situated near Jagiroad town, about 56 kilometers east of Guwahati, in the Morigaon District of Central Assam. Being one of the oldest public sector paper mills, its commercial production started in the year 1985. Around 600 acres of land was acquired for its establishment from both tribal and non-tribal populations residing in that area. However, according to the official records, only 84 families were displaced and compensation was paid to them. According to a report of the study conducted by the Assam Institute of Research for Tribal and Scheduled Castes, the compensation paid to the displaced people was Rs 6,300 per

Bighas (0.33 acres) for homestead and garden land. In the name of construction projects, the Tiwa people always face many problems. Due to their poor socio-economic conditions brought about by joblessness and poor yields from agriculture, young Tiwa boys have started to migrate to other parts of the country in search of livelihoods. There are cases of people moving out of their villages to work as security guards in Bangalore, Kerala, and other such jobs in different companies in Kolkata. Thus, the phenomenon of rural outmigration has started amongst them as well.⁴

Most significantly, for a variety of reasons the Tiwa Autonomous Council has not been able to achieve all of the goals for which it was founded. The Council is operating under numerous constraints. Another major issue facing the Tiwa Autonomous Councils is a lack of manpower. They must rely on the State Government to carry out their development projects. However, Because of the reason that they don't have the monitoring authority over the officials involved in carrying out the functions of the Council, some corrupt practices occur during the implementation of the schemes.

The government has always done its utmost to equalize and eventually improve all parts of society by enacting regulations and social programs. Along with government endeavors, awareness of the common people is highly important. To eradicate all problems from society and promote the entire community, proper use of public finances, research, and proper analysis of each project and its advantages are also very significant for the overall development of society.

⁴ . The Tiwas of Assam, (https://ebraby.net/238262/education/tiwas_assam).

Reference

Books

- Chowdhury, M. K. (2015). Economic Condition of Assam in Medieval Period: With Special Reference to Kamrup, *IJSSHR*, ISSN 2348-3164 (online) Vol. 3, Issue 4, pp: (86-97), December.
- Guha, A. (1991). *Medieval and Early Colonial Assam Society, Polity, Economy*, K.P.
- Bagchi & Company. Calcutta, New Delhi.
- Gohain, B.K. (1993). *The Hill Lalungs*, Anandaram Borooah Institute of Language, Art and Culture, Assam.
- Patar, R. (2021). *The Tiwa Ethnohistory*, The Notion Press, Tamilnadu.
- Thakur, Sharma, G.C. (1972). *The Plains Tribes of Lakhimpur, Dibrugarh, Sibsagar, And Nawgong*, pp 89- 99. Tribal Research Institute, Shillong.
- Von and Haimendorf, (1982). *Tribes of India the Struggle for Survival*, London, England.

Articles

- Purkayastha, N. (2015). Tribal Development Policies after Independence: A Study on Oraon Tribe in Barak Valley, *Region of Assam, International Journal in Management and Social Science*, Vol.03 Issue-07, July.
- Kachari, K. (2015). The Tiwa movement for identity in Assam and the issue of land alienation, *International Journal of English Language*, Vol 3, Issue 3, May.

Thesis

- Boruah. M. (2009), *Cultural Change in A Tribal Society: A Study on The Plain Tiwas Of Assam*, department of cultural studies. Tezpur University, Assam.
- Saloi, J. (2015). A study on the constitutional safeguards to the scheduled tribes in Assam with special reference to Lalung Tiwa tribe, Unpublished thesis, Department of Law, Gauhati University.

Government documents

- Directorate of Assam Institute of Research for Tribals & Scheduled Castes, *Ethnographic Museum*, Government of Assam, India.
- Department of Tribal Affairs (Plain), *Socio-Economic Upliftment*, Government of Assam, India
Office of the Director of Census Operations, *Census Report 2011*, Assam, Bhangagarh,
- Guwahati-781005 Online sources <https://www.census2011.co.in/census/district/157-karbi-anglong.html>). Accessed on August 2, 2024.
- The Tiwas of Assam, Nagaon Paper Mill (ebrary.net), Accessed from https://ebrary.net/238262/education/tiwas_assam#google_vignette, on September 10th, 2024.
- Protected tribal belts and blocks in Assam
https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/protected_tribal_belts_and_blocks_in_Assam#:~:text=The%20Protected%20Tribal%20Belts%20and,the%20first%20Chief%20Minister%20of, accessed on 10th September,2024.